

RESERVES, CONTINGENT LIABILITIES AND CONTINGENT ASSETS IN ACCORDANCE WITH THE INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL REPORTING STANDARD

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Abstract: In this article, the author examines the problems associated with the introduction of international financial reporting standards into the accounting system of Uzbekistan, suggests ways to solve them and describes the main advantages of their adoption.

Keywords: International Financial Reporting Standards, reporting, balance sheet.

International Standard IAS 37 "Reserves, Contingent Liabilities and Contingent Assets" defines the concepts of "reserves" ("estimated liabilities"¹), "contingent liabilities" and "contingent assets" and establishes the procedure for their recognition, accounting and reflection in the financial statements of organizations.

Thus, IFRS (IAS) 37 defines reserves as liabilities with an indefinite maturity or liabilities of an indefinite amount, while an obligation in the sense of IFRS (IAS) 37 (for the purposes of recognition in financial statements) is an existing obligation of an enterprise arising from past events, the settlement of which is expected to result in the disposal of resources from the enterprise containing economic benefits.

Unlike a provision or an estimated liability, a contingent liability is:

1. a possible obligation that arises from past events and the existence of which will be confirmed only by the occurrence or non-occurrence of one or more future

events, the occurrence of which is uncertain and which are not completely under the control of the organization; or

2. an existing obligation that arises from past events, but is not recognized because:

* it is not likely that an outflow of resources containing economic benefits will be required to settle the obligation;

* or the amount of the obligation cannot be estimated with a sufficient degree of reliability.

Finally, a conditional asset is a possible asset that arises from past events and the existence of which will be confirmed only by the occurrence or non-occurrence of one or more future events. Their occurrence is uncertain, and they are not completely under the control of the organization.

At the same time, paragraph 13 of IFRS 37 establishes clear differences between:

- reserves that are recognized as a liability (assuming that a reliable estimate can be obtained) because they represent existing liabilities and it is likely that an outflow of resources containing economic benefits will be required to settle the liabilities;

- contingent liabilities that are not recognized as an obligation because they are:

* possible obligations, since the existence of an existing obligation in the organization, which may lead to the outflow of resources containing economic benefits, requires additional confirmation;

* or existing liabilities that do not meet the recognition criteria established by this standard (because either it is not likely that an outflow of resources containing economic benefits will be required to settle the liability, or it is impossible to provide a sufficiently reliable estimate of the amount of the liability).

In accordance with the general procedure (see paragraph 14 of IAS 37 [1]), a provision should be recognized in cases where the following necessary conditions are met

- non-occurrence of one or more future events, the occurrence of which is uncertain and which are not completely under the control of the organization; or

- an existing obligation that arises from past events but is not recognized because:

- * it is not likely that an outflow of resources containing economic benefits will be required to settle the obligation;

- * or the amount of the obligation cannot be estimated with a sufficient degree of reliability.

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In accordance with the general procedure (see paragraph 14 of IAS 37 [1]), a provision should be recognized in cases where the following necessary conditions are met:

3. if settlements can be made forcibly in accordance with the legislation;

4. in the case of an obligation caused by practice, when such an event (which may be the action of the organization itself) creates reasonable expectations for other parties that the organization will fulfill this obligation.

In most practical cases, the identification of events that can be recognized as grounds for recognition of reserves does not cause serious difficulties, however, in practice there are various situations in which the fact of recognition of a reserve requires additional justification, or certain difficulties arise when forming rules for calculating a reserve in case of its unconditional recognition.

The first group of events is associated with a specific date of detection of binding events that serve as the basis for the recognition of reserves. Typical examples of events in this group are various situations in which tax risks associated with the implementation of various facts of economic life are identified, in particular, with the implementation of certain facts of economic life, as a result of which expenses arise that are recognized in the financial statements of the organization, but which with a high degree of probability may not be recognized as expenses that reduce the taxable profit of the organization. In particular, this applies to such facts of economic life (examples of which will be discussed below), for example:

* implementation of representative expenses,

* depreciation after modernization of fixed assets,

* accounting for expenses in the form of interest on controlled debt, in particular, on loans of subsidiaries received from foreign parent companies.

In these situations, tax risks arise due to the existence of different points of view of individual state regulatory authorities on the recognition of these types of expenses as reducing the taxable base for income tax, as well as various judicial practices.

When identifying such facts of economic life that contain tax risks, when forming financial statements, the probability of the outflow of resources that reduce economic benefits, when settling the obligations that have arisen, is significant, and the amount of reduction in economic benefits can be estimated, therefore, such tax risks should be recognized as reserves when forming financial statements in accordance with the rules of IFRS (IAS) 37.

Reference

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